

EARLY DETECTION OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14276673>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 29-noyabr 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 1-dekabr 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 4-dekabr 2024 yil

cardiovascular diseases, risk factors, young people, healthy lifestyle, cardiovascular disease prevention.

ABSTRACT

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) continue to occupy relevant positions in the context of modern healthcare problems. This pathology is characterized by high prevalence, frequency of complications and high level of disability and mortality among the working-age population. An important fact that alarms the medical community is not only the continuing trend towards an increase in morbidity, but also the so-called spread among the population that was previously less susceptible to the development of this pathology. This circumstance dictates the need to take into account the risk factors of CVD characteristic of young age. In order to solve this problem, it is first necessary to analyze the main risk factors influencing the development of CVD and develop scientifically based preventive measures for young people with a predisposition to the development of CVD, taking into account the prevalence of risk factors in modern socio-economic conditions. This will require activating the disease prevention system, both at the state level and at the level of practical healthcare services.

Introduction

The main risk factors for cardiovascular diseases are poor nutrition, insufficient physical activity, tobacco and alcohol consumption. An important phenomenon that worries the medical community is not only the continuing upward trend in incidence, but also its spread among the population that was previously less susceptible to the development of this pathology. This circumstance dictates the need to take into account the risk factors for CVD that are typical for young people.

Heart and vascular diseases remain one of the leading causes of death and disability in the world. However, early detection of cardiovascular diseases (CVD) can significantly improve the patient's prognosis, reduce the risk of complications and increase the effectiveness of

treatment. The importance of timely diagnosis can hardly be overestimated, since many diseases of the heart and blood vessels can be asymptomatic in the early stages, and their manifestations become noticeable only at later stages, when treatment may be less effective.

The main groups of diseases of the heart and blood vessels:

1. Atherosclerosis is a chronic disease of the arteries, in which atherosclerotic plaques form on their walls. This is the main cause of myocardial infarction, stroke and peripheral arterial disease.
2. Hypertension is high blood pressure, which can lead to heart failure, stroke and other complications.
3. Myocardial infarction is an acute disruption of the blood supply to the heart muscle that requires immediate intervention.
4. Heart failure is a condition in which the heart cannot effectively pump blood, which leads to fluid accumulation in the body and difficulty breathing.
5. Heart rhythm disorders (arrhythmias) are deviations from the normal heart rhythm that can be life-threatening if not detected in a timely manner.

Early detection of cardiovascular diseases

Early detection of CVD includes regular health monitoring, diagnostics and risk factor analysis.

The most effective diagnostic methods include:

1. **Questionnaire and anamnesis.** It is important to take into account family history of diseases, the presence of risk factors (smoking, physical inactivity, poor diet, stress, obesity, diabetes, etc.), the patient's age, gender, as well as his complaints and subjective symptoms (e.g. shortness of breath, chest pain, dizziness).
2. **Blood pressure measurement.** Regular blood pressure measurement is mandatory, since hypertension often has no obvious symptoms, but can lead to serious complications such as a heart attack or stroke.
3. **Electrocardiography (ECG).** This method allows you to evaluate the heart rhythm and identify abnormalities such as arrhythmia, signs of myocardial infarction or cardiac hypertrophy.
4. **Ultrasound examination of the heart (echocardiography).** This is an informative method that allows you to evaluate the structure and function of the heart, identify the presence of valve defects, and evaluate its pumping function.
5. **Tests for cholesterol and other lipids in the blood.** Measuring the levels of total cholesterol, LDL (bad) and HDL (good) cholesterol helps identify the risk of atherosclerosis and its complications.
6. **Holter monitoring.** This is a daily or multi-day monitoring of the electrical activity of the heart using a portable device. The method is useful for identifying hidden heart rhythm disturbances that may not be noticeable during a regular ECG.
7. **Stress tests.** These are studies conducted against the background of physical activity (for example, bicycle ergometry or treadmill) to check how the heart responds to physical exertion. Stress tests help identify hidden forms of coronary heart disease.

8. Coronavirus angiography (CAG). This is a more invasive method that is used to examine the vessels of the heart and identify atherosclerotic plaques. CAG is performed if coronary artery disease is suspected.

The importance of prevention

In addition to diagnosis, it is important to emphasize the importance of prevention. In the early stages, cardiovascular diseases can be corrected through lifestyle changes, medication, and regular monitoring.

Prevention of CVD includes:

1. *Healthy diet:* Reduce the consumption of saturated fats, sugar, and salt, and increase the proportion of vegetables, fruits, cereals, and healthy fats such as omega-3 fatty acids.
2. *Physical activity:* Regular aerobic exercise (e.g. brisk walking, swimming, running), which helps maintain normal cholesterol levels and blood pressure.
3. *Smoking cessation:* Smoking is one of the main risk factors for the development of CVD, as it damages blood vessels and promotes the formation of atherosclerotic plaques.
4. *Weight control:* Obesity increases the risk of hypertension, diabetes, and other cardiovascular diseases.
5. *Stress management:* Chronic stress can contribute to high blood pressure and heart disease.
6. *Regular medical monitoring:* Particular attention should be paid to people with a predisposition to cardiovascular disease (for example, high blood pressure, diabetes, or a family history of CVD).

Conclusion

Early detection of heart and vascular diseases is a key factor in preventing serious complications such as myocardial infarction, stroke and heart failure. Timely diagnosis and prevention of diseases can not only improve the quality of life, but also significantly reduce the financial burden on health care. It is important to remember that effective management of heart health requires combining regular examinations with an active lifestyle and proper nutrition.

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